

Synthesis and biocidal activity of some new 2-amino-4,6-diaryl-substituted-pyrimidines

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The chalcones (3a-q), derived from 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone (1a), 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone (1b), 3-bromo-5-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenones (1c,d) and 4-(4'-nitrophenoxy)acetophenone (1e) and prepared by Claisen-Schmidt condensation with different substituted aromatic aldehydes (2a-f) in presence of base, on treatment with guanidine nitrate in ethanol and base give new 2-amino-4,6-diaryl-substituted-pyrimidines (4a-q). The compounds have been screened for their antibacterial and herbicidal activities.

Much attention has been given on the synthesis of pyrimidines possessing a variety of pharmacological activities¹. Our continued interest in the synthesis of biologically active nitrogen heterocycles prompted us to synthesise various substituted 2-amino-4,6-diarylpyrimidines and evaluate their possible herbicidal and antibacterial activities.

The synthesis of substituted pyrimidines from α,β -unsaturated ketones was reported². Phenolic ketones bearing halogen atoms in their nucleus and their phenoxy derivatives are of diverse biological interest. 4-Hydroxyacetophenone bearing halogen substituents in the 3 and 5 positions are structurally related to antagonists of thyroxine³ and diphenyl ethers are found to have pesticidal⁴ and herbicidal⁵ activities. In the present studies we envisage that compounds incorporating these moieties in their molecular framework may be associated with enhanced physiological activity and hence the title investigation according to reaction sequence shown in the Scheme 1.

Results and Discussion

4-(4'-Nitrophenoxy)acetophenone (1e) was prepared by the reaction of *p*-hydroxyacetophenone with *p*-chloro-nitrobenzene. Base catalysed condensation of substituted acetophenones (1a-e) with different aromatic aldehydes (2a-f) led to the corresponding chalcones (3a-q). Compounds 3a-q on reaction with guanidine nitrate yielded 2-amino-4,6-diaryl-substituted-pyrimidines (4a-q). Mechanistically, in presence of base, guanidine nitrate is converted to free base which can act as a bidentate nucleophile and facilitate Michael type addition with α,β -unsaturated system of chalcones (3) or internal condensation with carbonyl group of 3 followed by cyclisation will result in the unstable dihydropyrimidine derivatives which in presence of air are dehydrogenated to yield (4a-q).

Biological activity : All the compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus*, *S. albus*, *S. pyogenes*, *S. viridans* and Gram-negative bacteria *K. pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, *P. mirabilis* and *S. typhosa* at 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration in DMF following paper disc diffusion technique using gentamycin as standard.

3,5-Dibromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone (1a) exhibited significant activity whereas acetophenone (1e) was moderately active against *S. aureus*.

Amongst the chalcones, 3b,c showed excellent activity whereas 3a,d,e,f,k,i showed moderate activity against *S. aureus*. Compounds 3a,d,e and 3f,k,i were found moderately active against *S. pyogenes* and *S. albus*, respectively. Compounds 3m,n,o,q exhibited moderate to excellent activity against *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. All other compounds did not show significant activity against the tested microorganisms.

2-Aminopyrimidine derivatives 4a,b showed significant activity and 4e,d showed moderate activity against *E. coli*. Compounds 4a-h exhibited moderate activity whereas compound 4f showed significant activity against *S. aureus*. Compounds 4a-e were inactive against *S. viridans* and *S. pyogenes*. All other compounds did not possess significant activity against the tested bacteria.

Herbicidal activity : Compounds 1a,e, 3a-e,k-q, 4a-e and 4l-q were tested for herbicidal activity against eighteen individually potted plants of economically important weeds and crops. The minimum sample used for this test was 250 mg. Acetophenone 1e, chalcones 3b,d,o and pyrimidines 4a,b,e,m showed moderate herbicidal activity. All other tested compounds were found inactive as fungicidal, insecticidal and in animal health screen.

- 1a** R₃ = H, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = OH
b R₃ = OH, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = H
c R₃ = OH, R₄ = Br, R₅ = H, R₆ = CH₃
d R₃ = OH, R₄ = Br, R₅ = H, R₆ = Cl
e R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂
- 2a** R₁ = R₂ = H
b R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = H
c R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H
d R₁ = Cl, R₂ = H
e R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃
f R₁ = H, R₂ = NO₂

3a-q

- 3,4 a** R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = OH
b R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = OH
c R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = OH
d R₁ = Cl, R₂ = R₃ = H, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = OH
e R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = H, R₄ = R₆ = Br, R₅ = OH
f R₁ = R₂ = R₅ = H, R₃ = OH, R₄ = R₆ = Br
g R₁ = R₂ = R₅ = H, R₃ = OH, R₄ = Br, R₆ = CH₃
h R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₅ = H, R₃ = OH, R₄ = Br, R₆ = Cl
i R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₅ = H, R₃ = OH, R₄ = R₆ = Br
j R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₅ = H, R₃ = OH, R₄ = Br, R₆ = CH₃
k R₁ = Cl, R₂ = R₅ = H, R₃ = OH, R₄ = R₆ = Br
l R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂
m R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂
n R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂
o R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂
p R₁ = R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₂ = NO₂, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂
q R₁ = Cl, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = R₆ = H, R₅ = OC₆H₄-*p*-NO₂

Scheme 1

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in open capillaries and uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) : Perkin-Elmer-881, 557; PMR spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO_d₆); Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard; mass spectra Jeol-D-300 spectrometer. All compounds gave satisfactory micro-analytical results.

4-(4'-Nitrophenoxy)acetophenone (1e) : A mixture of *p*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.014 mol), *p*-chloronitrobenzene

(0.015 mol) and anhyd. potassium carbonate (2.5 g) and DMF (20 ml) was refluxed for 8 h and the completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The mixture was then filtered and the residue washed with DMF (2 × 10 ml). The combined filtrate was concentrated, cooled and diluted with water. A brown coloured solid that separated out on keeping the solution in refrigerator, crystallized from ethanol as light brown needles (58%), m.p. 64° (Found : C, 64.62; H, 4.11; N, 5.36. C₁₄H₁₁O₄N (257.25) requires : C, 65.35; H, 4.20; N, 5.41%); ν_{max} 1660 (CO), 1600–1450 (aromatic), 830–750 (*p*-subst. benzene), 1570, 1360 (NO₂), 1250, 1150 cm⁻¹ (Ar-O-Ar); δ (CDCl₃) 2.68 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.07–8.22 (8H, m, ArH); *m/z* 257 (M⁺), 242 (100%), 196, 168, 139, 92, 76, 50 and 43.

3,5-Dibromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone (1a)³ and **2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-bromo/methyl/chloro-substituted-acetophenones (1b-d)⁶** were synthesised by reported methods.

1-(3,5-Dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (3a) : To a well-stirred and cooled solution of 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was added 50% aqueous NaOH (10 ml) during a period of 20 min. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature. It was then poured on crushed ice, acidified with HCl (6 N) and the resulting yellow orange solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (90%) as fine yellow needles (50%), m.p. 161°; ν_{max} 3500–3100 (H-bonded OH), 1680 (CO), 1600, 1580 (C=C) 950–650 cm⁻¹ (substituted benzene); δ (CDCl₃) 6.94 (3H, m, C₃-H, C₄-H and C₅-H from ring-B), 7.07–7.18 (2H, m, C₂-H, C₆-H from B-ring), 7.40 (2H, d, C₂'-H, C₆'-H from A-ring), 7.60 (1H, d, α-H), 7.84 (1H, d, β-H), 8.22 (1H, s, OH); *m/z* (%) 382 (M⁺), (16.7), 684 (M+2)⁺ (12.9), 381 (22.4), 380 (28.1), 302 (8.7), 278 (8.9), 251 (24.1), 194 (11.0), 151 (21.6), 131 (28.2). Similarly, other compounds (50–80%) were prepared : **3b** m.p. 168°; **c**, 171°; **d**, 148°; **e**, 100°; **f**, 145°; **g**, 110°; **h**, 165°; **i**, 165°; **j**, 149°; **k**, 195°; **l**, 155°; **m**, 128°; **n**, 151°; **o**, 122°; **p**, 210°; **q**, 190°.

2-Amino-4-(3',5'-dibromo-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (4a) : To a refluxing mixture of the chalcone (**3a**; 0.1 mol) and guanidine nitrate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added aqueous NaOH (40%; 5 ml) portionwise during a period of 3 h and refluxing continued for 5 h (monitored by TLC). The solvent was then distilled off and the mixture was diluted with water. The resultant solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene as light brown needles (45%), m.p. 145° (Found : C, 45.68; H, 2.9; N, 10.02. C₁₆H₁₁ON₃Br₂ requires : C, 45.64; H, 2.63; N, 9.98%); ν_{max} 3440–3330 (NH₂), 1620 (C=N), 1600–1500, 877–740 cm⁻¹ (aromatic, substituted phenyl ring); δ

(CDCl₃) 5.2 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.55 (1H, s, H-5 of pyrimidine ring), 7.8–8.1 (7H, m, ArH) and 8.5 (1H, s, OH); *m/z* (%) 420 (M⁺) (4.2), 422 (M+2)⁺ (3.1), 293 (20.1), 280 (38.6), 278 (77.0), 276 (41.2), 250 (7.4), 222 (5.9), 170 (16.1) and 143 (9.4). Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 40–60%). **4b**, m.p. 210°, **c**, 228°; **d**, 205°; **e**, 140°; **f**, 190°; **g-k** >290°, **l**, 182°; **m**, 218°; **n**, 188°; **o**, 180°; **p**, 198°; **q**, 130°.

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